

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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HEADSPACE: ENCOURAGING STRESS REDUCTION AND MINDFULNESS IN FIRST
RESPONDERS THROUGH USING A MOBILE APPLICATION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Background: Stress has become increasingly prevalent in modern society, contributing to various negative health outcomes. Mindfulness interventions have emerged as promising strategies for stress reduction and improving overall well-being. This quality improvement project aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of a mobile mindfulness intervention, specifically the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app, in reducing perceived stress and enhancing mindfulness levels among first responders. Methods: A pre-post design was employed to assess changes in stress levels and mindfulness before and after engaging with the Headspace app. Participants (n=13) were recruited via mass email. They completed validated self-report measures, including the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) and the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS-15), before and after a 21-day intervention period using the Headspace app. Data were analyzed using paired samples t-tests to examine pre-post changes in stress and mindfulness levels. Results: Preliminary data analysis revealed a significant decrease in mean scores on the PSS-10 scale ($p < .001$), indicating a reduction in perceived stress levels following the intervention. Additionally, there was a significant increase in mean scores on the MAAS-15 scale ($p < .001$), indicating an improvement in mindfulness levels post-intervention. Conclusion: The Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app may reduce stress and enhance mindfulness. Integrating mobile mindfulness interventions into law enforcement may improve quality of life and address stress-related concerns. Further investigation in larger studies with first responders is needed.

Keywords: first responders, police officers, stress, PTSD, mindfulness, Headspace, occupational hazards, peer reviewed.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vi
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	2
Purpose Statement.....	5
Theoretical Framework.....	5
Framework Discussion.....	6
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	10
Multiple Stressors	11
Sleep Deprivation.....	11
Shift Work.....	12
Depression.....	13
PTSD.....	13
Substance Use	14
Protective Factors.....	14
Resilience.....	15
Mindfulness.....	15
Coping Strategies	16
Evidence-Based Approaches	17
Headspace Mindfulness Mobile App.....	17
METHODS	19
Design	19
Setting	19
Sample.....	19
Institutional Review Board Approval	20
Planning	20
Measures	21
Data Analysis	21
RESULTS	22

PSS-10 Results.....	22
MAAS-15 Results.....	22
DISCUSSION.....	24
Recommendations.....	24
Limitations	25
Implications for practice	26
Conclusion	26
REFERENCES	27
APPENDIX A:	
Figure 1: Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence Based Practice Model	34
Figure 1.2: Permission to use Johns Hopkins EBP (Evidence Based Practice) Model	35
APPENDIX B:	
Figure 2: Perceived Stress Scale	36
Figure 2.1 Permission to use Perceived Stress Scale.....	37
APPENDIX C:	
Figure 3: Mindful Attention Awareness Scale.....	38
Figure 3.1 Permission to use Mindful Attention Awareness Scale	39
APPENDIX D: IRB (Institutional Review Board) Approval.....	40
APPENDIX E: Figure 4: Letter of Support	41
APPENDIX F: Table 1: Participant Sociodemographic.....	42
APPENDIX G: Figure 6: Mean Pre and Post PSS-10 scores	43
APPENDIX H: Table 2: T-test Pre and Post PSS-10 scores	44
APPENDIX I: Figure 7: Mean Pre and Post MAAS-15 scores.....	45
APPENDIX J: Table 3: T-tests Pre and Post MAAS-15 scores	46

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Background

First responders, including police officers, dispatchers, forensic professionals, and healthcare workers, play a vital role in society, often being the first to confront complex, hazardous, and demanding situations (Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration [SAMHSA], 2018). This unwavering dedication comes at a cost: these individuals frequently operate in highly stressful and traumatic environments, which take a toll on their mental well-being. Some of the challenges faced by first responders include increased incidence of anxiety disorders, depression, burnout, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), suicide, alcohol, and drug misuse, as well as poor sleep hygiene and impaired coping, compared to the general working population (Thompson & Drew, 2020). These occupational hazards result from constant exposure to distressing events and irregular sleep schedules (Jones, 2017).

A staggering 30% of first responders experience behavioral health disorders, with conditions like depression and PTSD being prevalent (Luster, 2022). Among those diagnosed with PTSD, a significant proportion also grapple with substance use disorder (SUD) (Thompson & Drew, 2020). Notably, police personnel exhibit a PTSD prevalence rate of 4.7%, with higher rates among women (15.5%) than men (10.3%) (SAMHSA, 2018). PTSD has an impact on around 3.5 percent of individuals in the United States annually. The overall occurrence rate of PTSD among teenagers between the ages of 13 and 18 is 8%. Approximately 1 in 11 individuals may receive a diagnosis of PTSD at some point in their lives (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2022).

In their line of duty, first responders frequently witness harrowing situations, from tragic accidents to natural disasters and acts of violence (Jones, 2017). One such incidence, the World Trade Center attacks, led to 11% of respondents developing PTSD, with half experiencing

anxiety and depression (Cone et al., 2015). Suicide rates among police officers and public safety workers remain alarmingly high, with an estimated 125 to 300 police personnel ending their lives each year (Luster, 2022).

Problem Statement

First responders are often exposed to traumatic situations and high stress in their line of duty. Stress is a psychological and physiological response to a perceived threat or challenge that requires an adaptive response by the individual experiencing it (Chu et al., 2019). The prevalent mental health challenges faced by first responders, including police officers, dispatchers, and forensic professionals, are significant and multifaceted. These challenges stem from their exposure to highly stressful and traumatic environments, leading to various mental health issues. Some of the key challenges include anxiety disorders, depression, burnout, PTSD, suicide, substance misuse, and poor sleep hygiene (Chu et al., 2019; SAMHSA, 2018; Saunders et al., 2019).

These mental health challenges are exacerbated by cumulative exposure to distressing events, long hours, and insufficient resources, leading to unintentional challenges. It is crucial to address these challenges and provide effective coping strategies and interventions to support first responders' mental health and well-being. These stressors can have a profound impact on the first responder's mental health (Chu et al., 2019; SAMHSA, 2018; Saunders et al., 2019).

Suicide accounted for twice as many officer fatalities in 2019 as deaths in the line of duty (Jetelina et al., 2020). Research supports the notion that police officers have a greater incidence of cardiovascular illness compared to the general population. Furthermore, mortality studies demonstrate that officers have a shorter lifespan compared to the overall population of the United States (Violanti et al., 2020).

One of the primary causes of mortality among police officers in the United States was occupational ailments. The National Law Enforcement Officers Memorial Fund (NLEOMF) received reports of 3,645 police fatalities throughout a 22-year study period. Moreover, six hundred and forty-six of these fatalities were ascribed to occupational ailments (Violanti et al., 2020).

Effective coping strategies can reduce the high stress and traumatic events that first responders witness. Some effective coping strategies are cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), eye movement desensitization and reprocessing, exercise, and mindfulness meditation, which participants can access more readily through a smartphone app.

Evidence-based interventions, such as CBT, peer support programs, and mindfulness-based therapies, play a crucial role in improving the mental well-being of first responders (Meckes et al., 2021; Zollars et al., 2019; Alden et al., 2021). These are shown to be effective in addressing the unique challenges faced by first responders, including anxiety disorders, depression, burnout, PTSD, and substance misuse (Meckes et al., 2021; Zollars et al., 2019; Alden et al., 2021).

Mindfulness training, which entails observing thoughts and feelings without responding or passing judgment, has been demonstrated to enhance various aspects of psychological well-being. Mindfulness intervention has a significant positive impact on irritability and stress. Mindfulness increases awareness of thoughts, emotions, and physical sensations while keeping an open mind free from distraction and judgment (Bostock et al., 2019; Chopko et al., 2018; Economides et al., 2018).

In a study conducted by Hoeve et al., 2021, police officers demonstrated substantial enhancements in stress levels and various aspects of mindful awareness following the

intervention of mindfulness meditation (Hoeve et al., 2021). Mindfulness reduces the connection between chronic stress and pain disruption (Colgan et al., 2019), workload and both mental and physical symptoms of strain (Fisher et al., 2019), and occupational stressors and perceived stress (Hoeve et al., 2021; Kaplan et al., 2018).

Smartphone applications (apps) are increasingly popular for interventions to decrease perceived stress due to their affordability, versatility, and wide availability (Champion et al., 2018). There are approximately 3.2 billion active cellphone users worldwide. Modern cell phones are lightweight, simple to use, and serve many apps. Mobile apps are ideal for disseminating health information because they allow people to handle their needs discreetly and without judgment. Individuals can select an app depending on their mental health needs and personalize the app to manage their symptoms and severity. Utilizing cutting-edge mobile technology, such as a smartphone, allows individuals who would not usually seek medical assistance due to social stigma, geographical limitations, or time constraints to get treatment at their convenience through their mobile device (Willis et al., 2020).

One such app, Headspace (Economides et al., 2018), offers a convenient platform for daily mindfulness meditation, potentially reducing perceived stress and increasing mindfulness among first responders (Champion et al., 2018). Headspace therapy decreased depression in 75% of trials that looked at it as an endpoint. The results of mindfulness, well-being, stress, and anxiety were inconsistent, but at least 40% of trials demonstrated improvement in each area (O'Daffer et al., 2022). Using the Headspace app, participants reported various mindfulness practice experiences. Mindfulness practice resulted in developing new, nonjudgmental attitudes toward experience and recognizing accessible choices (Strauss et al., 2021).

Purpose Statement

The Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aimed to introduce the Headspace app to participating first responders and implement a 21-day mindfulness meditation program to decrease perceived stress and increase mindfulness. The paper also presents a detailed literature review covering various stressors first responders encounter, such as exposure to traumatic events, sleep deprivation, and shift work, along with the evidence-based approaches and protective factors that can help decrease stress and increase mindfulness among this demographic. Furthermore, it discusses the potential impact of implementing the Headspace app for first responders, drawing on evidence from randomized controlled trials and pilot studies.

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aimed to address the contributing factors that increase stress levels, which cause health risks and lead to burnout and decreased mindfulness in first responders, including police officers, dispatchers, and forensic specialists employed at a local police department in Southern California.

This quality improvement project was guided by the following PICO question:

"Does implementing the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app decrease perceived stress and increase mindfulness in first responders?"

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework is essential for linking a project question and study objectives to guided practice (Holly, 2019). Using a framework enables a systematic approach to evaluating a problem, implementing a practice change, and assessing the intervention's efficacy. Conceptual models help clarify and organize complex ideas or systems for better understanding.

Additionally, they provide a high-level representation of key concepts, relationships, and processes within a particular domain or problem (Ravitch & Riggan, 2016).

Framework Discussion

The theoretical framework for this DNP project was the Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice (JHNEBP) Model. This model is designed to guide the systematic evaluation of problems, implementation of practice changes, and evaluation of intervention efficacy (Dang et al., 2022). The JHNEBP Model focuses on the needs of researchers, facilitating the quick and appropriate utilization of recent research and best practices. It streamlines the EBP procedure and nurtures a culture of evidence-based practice (Wyant, 2017Alden).

Numerous studies have shown how widely the JHNEBP Model is used in healthcare research. For instance, Anioche and Clark (2017) published a survey for the Association for Peri-Operative Registered Nurses using the JHNEBP Model to critically appraise studies, determining the quality and strength of the reviewed evidence. In the same way, the Journal of Peri-Anesthesia Nursing evaluated nineteen articles using the Model. This Model made staff more aware of how vital evidence-based practice is and encouraged them to use complementary techniques to ensure optimal patient outcomes in the Post-Anesthesia Care Unit (Anicoche & Kaiser, 2021). These examples illustrate the widespread use of the JHNEBP Model in healthcare research, guiding the development and implementation of evidence-based clinical practices. The Model comprises three main steps: practice questions, evidence, and translation. Its guiding tools support individual and group work, enabling practicing clinicians to address clinical queries effectively (Wyant, 2017).

In the first step of the JHNEBP Model, the project lead formulates a well-structured clinical question focused on a specific population or problem. The clinical question is: "Does implementing the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app decrease perceived stress and increase mindfulness in first responders?" The JHNEBP Model recommends utilizing the patient,

intervention, comparison, outcome, and time framework to create a clear and precise question, aiding in the practical search and evaluation of the best available evidence to inform practice and decision-making (Dang et al., 2022). To ensure a comprehensive approach, critical stakeholders, including law enforcement personnel, leadership, and mental health leadership, will be engaged and informed that a needs assessment will be conducted to gauge first responders' self-reported stress levels and willingness to use a mindfulness mobile app like Headspace.

The second step involved acquiring the best available evidence to answer the question. During this phase, the project lead searched for relevant evidence from peer-reviewed journals, clinical practice guidelines, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and other databases. The evidence directly addressed the clinical question formulated in the first step and was critically appraised for its quality and relevance to the identified problem (Dang et al., 2022). Within step two, the appraisal is a critical component. This phase involved critically evaluating the acquired evidence, considering quality, validity, and relevance to the clinical question. The project lead assessed the study design, methodology, and results to determine the level of evidence provided and the strength of the findings (Dang et al., 2022).

The project lead critically evaluated the acquired literature and found sufficient evidence to support the implementation of the Headspace Mindfulness Meditation app. The evidence supports implementing the app to enhance the quality of life, mindfulness, well-being, and stress (Rosen et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018).

The final step in the JHNEBP Model is to translate and apply the evidence in the clinical decision-making process. Mimicking the JHNEBP Framework will introduce the Headspace mobile app to first responders and incorporate it into their daily practice. The project lead assessed the effectiveness of the Headspace mobile app through pre- and post-surveys of

participants' perceived stress scale -10 (PSS-10) and mindful attention awareness scale -15 (MAAS-15) scores. The PSS-10 survey asks about feelings and perceived stress (Figure 2; Champion et al., 2018). The 10-item scale measures participants' perceptions of their lives as unpredictable, unmanageable, and overloaded compared to the previous month. Participants used a 5-point Likert scale to answer questions about their emotions and thoughts (0 = never to 4 = very often). Increased ratings indicate more stress. Ratings range from 0 to 40 (Champion et al., 2018).

The MAAS-15 survey, assesses an individual's level of trait mindfulness (Figure 3). The MAAS quantifies the rate at which individuals exhibit open and receptive attention to and awareness of ongoing events and experiences. The response options range from (1 = never to 6 = always) (Black et al., 2012). Feedback from these surveys will inform future implementation efforts and be shared with the local police department and key stakeholders to promote evidence-based interventions for improving first responders' well-being. The project lead conducted a ten-minute briefing for participants to discuss the project's purpose, benefits, timeline, and mindfulness app usage.

The pilot project's procedures were rigorously followed, including recruitment, intervention, implementation, pre-post surveys, and progress sharing. Data analysis of pre-post and feasibility surveys revealed enhanced results and sustainability information. For instance, if the poll survey results indicate decreased perceived stress and increased mindfulness, the agency may consider adopting a mobile mindfulness app. The project lead integrated the evidence gathered and critically appraised it with their clinical expertise and patient values to make an informed decision or make recommendations for practice. The project lead collaborated with stakeholders and aligned evidence and intentions for translation into practice.

Review of Literature

A literature review helps uncover the existing research and knowledge on a specific topic. A thorough literature review reveals fundamental theories, concepts, methodologies, and findings in the field of study and identifies gaps or unanswered questions in the current knowledge. This helps determine the relevance and novelty of a scholarly project and provides a foundation for developing research objectives and hypotheses. Finally, the findings from a literature review can inform decision-making processes. Whether designing a research study, developing interventions or policies, or making informed judgments, the knowledge gained from a literature review helps ensure that decisions are evidence-based and informed by the current state of knowledge.

A literature review was performed using the following search engines: One Search, PubMed, PsycINFO, Cinahl, and Google Scholar. Keywords used in the search were "first responders," "police officers," "stress," "PTSD," "mindfulness," "Headspace," and "peer reviewed." The search was limited to peer-reviewed, English-language studies published between 2018 and 2022. This search yielded 63 articles. Thirty-six articles were chosen to validate project interventions.

The search approach used Boolean operators to combine search phrases, filters, and limiters to narrow results. If articles were duplicated, irrelevant, or excluded, they were removed. After duplicates were removed, all abstracts were reviewed for relevance and fit. Inclusion criteria included Police officers, dispatchers, forensic specialists, first responders, 18 years and older, employed by this law enforcement agency in Southern California, has possession of a cellphone, and the ability to download the Headspace app. Exclusion criteria included anyone under 18 years of age, not employed by this law enforcement agency, not possessing a cellphone,

and needing help to download the Headspace app. Smartphone apps are increasingly popular for interventions due to their affordability, versatility, and wide availability (Champion et al., 2018). The themes were identified and classified using thematic analysis. Finally, the topics were synthesized to draw conclusions and shape the quality improvement initiative.

First responders, stress, and mindfulness have all been thoroughly covered in literature, which acknowledges the difficulties these individuals experience and the possible advantages of mindfulness techniques. While the literature supports the potential benefits of mindfulness for first responders in managing stress, promoting mental health, and improving job performance, further research is needed to explore optimal delivery methods, long-term effects, and the specific impacts on different subgroups of first responders.

Multiple Stressors

Several studies found a correlation between increased stress and occupational ailments in first responders (Alden et al., 2021; Jones, 2017; Ponder et al., 2021; Saunders et al., 2019). Officers encounter daily stressors connected to their jobs, ranging from interpersonal problems to severely horrific situations, including car accidents, homicides, and suicides. In addition, officers' mental and physical health may be impacted by cumulative exposure, which means the stressors they encounter over time. Cumulative exposure may increase the risk of developing depression, anxiety, burnout, suicidal thoughts, alcohol substance abuse, PTSD symptoms, inadequate sleep, and anger management issues (Alden et al., 2021; Carlton et al., 2018; Saunders et al., 2019; Thompson & Drew, 2020).

Sleep Deprivation

Sleep deprivation, common among first responders, is defined as fewer than four to six hours of sleep in 24 hours. Sleep deprivation can lead to fatigue, decreased alertness, and poor

concentration due to hours of operation, the nature of the profession, and shift work (Jones, 2017; National Officer Safety Initiative [NOSI], 2018). Sleep deprivation contributes to a decreased quality of life, mood disturbances, and cognitive impairments (Jones, 2017). Sleep is a biological process for memory, emotion, learning, metabolic control, cellular toxin clearance, and human neural growth. Poor sleep has serious health consequences because it disrupts circadian rhythms, essential for maintaining survival, recovery, and energy conservation, all of which are critical for good health and an enhanced quality of life (Huang et al., 2022).

Melatonin production is regulated by circadian rhythms, which also control other bodily functions. Long-term consequences of poor sleep hygiene include an increased risk for obesity, cancer and cardiovascular disease. Short-term repercussions of poor sleep hygiene include difficulties concentrating, mood disturbances, and headaches (Huang et al., 2022). Therefore, investigating sleep issues in first responders is essential to preventing physical and mental complications and ensuring service delivery to this demographic (Huang et al., 2022; Jones, 2017; NOSI, 2018).

Shift Work

Although shiftwork is sometimes necessary for many professions, people who work in protective services frequently utilize it. Working nights or switching between day, evening, and night shifts is considered shiftwork. Shiftwork has been linked to several physical and mental health problems, including heart disease, cancer, depression, lowered immune system, and sleep disturbances (NOSI, 2020; Shockey et al., 2022). Working night shifts increases the chance of injury and the incidence of long-term (>90 days) damage. For example, approximately 34% of officers who worked night shifts took a vacation for fewer than 15 days (about 2 weeks), twice

the national median of 15 days (about 2 weeks) reported by the Bureau of Labor Statistics (NOSI, 2020; Shockey et al., 2022).

Depression

Police personnel suffer from depression (SAMHSA, 2018). For example, following police personnel after the 9/11 attacks, the researchers discovered a 24.7% depression prevalence and a combined 47.7% depression and anxiety prevalence (SAMHSA, 2018). In the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), major depressive disorder (MDD) is characterized by a loss of pleasure or a depressed mood that lasts for most of the day, every day for at least two weeks and causes severe functional impairments in a variety of circumstances (American Psychological Association [APA], 2019; Jones, 2017). Symptoms include appetite and weight changes, fatigue or low energy, sleep changes, psychomotor agitation, feelings of worthlessness or guilt, decreased concentration, and reoccurring thoughts of death or suicide (APA, 2019; Jones, 2017).

There is an association between MDD and PTSD. Suicidality is strongly correlated with MDD and PTSD, and the symptoms are more severe when they co-occur. Comorbidity prevalence rates range from 21% to 95%, and the seriousness of trauma exposure frequently predicts the comorbidity prevalence rates. (APA, 2019; Jones, 2017).

PTSD

PTSD affect anyone who has experienced or witnessed a traumatic event, including first responders such as police officers, firefighters, and emergency medical personnel. First responders are often exposed to highly stressful and traumatic situations as part of their job, such as responding to violent crimes, accidents, natural disasters, and other emergencies. These experiences can lead to PTSD development, characterized by symptoms such as flashbacks,

nightmares, anxiety, depression, and hyper-vigilance. The prevalence of PTSD among first responders is estimated to be higher than in the general population, and it can significantly impact their mental health, personal relationships, and ability to perform their job duties (Jones, 2017; NOSI, 2020).

Substance Use

The DSM-5 defines Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD) as problematic patterns of alcohol use that lead to impairments or distress (APA, 2019; Jones, 2017). AUD increases suicide attempt risk. The practice of drinking is widespread among law enforcement personnel. For women, a binge is defined as four or more drinks, while for men, a binge is defined as five or more drinks. Adults consume 17 billion binge drinks every year, which averages up to 467 binge drinks per adult who engages in binge drinking (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2024). Drinking is frequently done to unwind after a shift and ease anxiety (Jones, 2017; NOSI, 2020).

In a study investigating alcohol use by police officers following Hurricane Katrina, there was a significant association between involvement in hurricane relief efforts and hazardous alcohol drinking (SAMHSA, 2018). In another study, the average number of alcoholic drinks after Hurricane Katrina increased from two to seven per day (SAMHSA, 2018).

Protective Factors

Several protective factors can help first responders decrease stress and increase mindfulness. To prevent or reduce stressors, there must be greater access to high-quality mental health and wellness treatments delivered by knowledgeable clinicians. One organization claimed to have implemented a restorative sleep policy that encouraged officers to nap during lunch breaks and constructed sleep rooms (NOSI, 2020). Another initiative aimed to boost officer and family peer support program participation (NOSI, 2020).

Resilience

Developing resilience, or the ability to bounce back from difficult situations, can help first responders cope with the challenges of the job and maintain a positive outlook. Programs designed to increase resilience focus on various issues, including self-control, self-awareness, self-efficacy, fear response, emotional regulation, and problem-solving (NOSI, 2020). For example, mindfulness-based resilience training improved mental health measures in law enforcement officers (McDonald et al., 2021; NOSI, 2020).

Mindfulness

Mindfulness training enables people to focus their attention on present-moment sensations without passing judgment (NOSI, 2020). This training can help police officers manage stress and have better coping mechanisms for trauma and crises. Interventions focused on mindfulness may help police deal with and reduce stress and improve resilience, burnout, rage, exhaustion, and sleep disturbance (Chopko et al., 2018; NOSI, 2020; Thompson & Drew, 2020).

Thompson and Drew (2020) created Warrior21, a 21-day mindfulness, cognitive restructuring, and self-compassion program for first responders. First responders enjoyed the program that was created for them. The authors proposed that Warrior21 can help first responders enhance resilience and mental health. Mindfulness-based therapies for first responders are gaining favor, but additional study is needed to evaluate their best delivery format and length. In addition, mindfulness-based interventions must also address first responders' unique demands. For example, first responders may benefit from treatments focusing on critical event management or communication.

Coping Strategies

First responders frequently encounter difficult and trying circumstances that can harm their mental health. Creating efficient coping mechanisms is crucial to guaranteeing their well-being. In 2003, the American Psychological Association released a paper with recommendations for first responders dealing with change. To handle the job's rigors, the study strongly emphasizes developing resilience, upholding healthy relationships, and managing stress (Newman, 2003).

Saunders, Kotzias, and Ramchand (2019) also looked at the effects of the changing socio-political environment on the mental health of first responders and the stress experienced by today's police officers. The authors contended that because of their employment, first responders suffer difficulties such as exposure to violence and trauma, long hours, and insufficient resources. Chronic stress brought on by these difficulties may negatively affect physical and emotional well-being (Saunders et al., 2019).

Organizations should adopt a comprehensive strategy for supporting first responders' mental health to address these issues. This entails making mental health treatments accessible, encouraging healthy lifestyles, and developing a positive workplace atmosphere. In addition, according to Saunders et al. (2019), businesses should regularly provide training on stress management and coping mechanisms to aid first responders in acquiring the abilities they need to handle the demands of their jobs.

Peer support initiatives have also been proven successful in enhancing first responders' mental health. assistance. According to Alden et al. (2021), peer support programs are an evidence-based strategy that has successfully enhanced first responders' mental health.

Evidence-Based Approaches

CBT is a talk therapy that helps individuals recognize and alter harmful thought patterns and behaviors that cause mental health concerns. It has been particularly effective in helping first responders with PTSD and depression (Alden et al., 2021). Additionally, peer support programs, which involve trained peers providing emotional assistance to colleagues, have been successful in helping first responders cope with PTSD and depression (Alden et al., 2021).

Critical incident stress debriefing (CISD) is a structured group technique that helps people cope with stressful circumstances. First responders are often given CISD to prevent PTSD and other mental health disorders. However, CISD may not prevent PTSD and may potentially worsen it, according to some researchers (Alden et al., 2021). Hence, CISD's efficacy for first responders needs further exploration.

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, peer support, and mindfulness-based therapies have improved first responders' mental health. However, these therapies' efficacy depends on individual and organizational characteristics. So, research and implementation of evidence-based mental health therapies for first responders are crucial.

Headspace Mindfulness App

The potential benefits of implementing the Headspace mindfulness mobile app for first responders are significant. The app offers a convenient platform for daily mindfulness meditation, potentially reducing perceived stress and increasing mindfulness among first responders. Studies have shown that the use of the Headspace app has led to improvements in depression, global well-being, anxiety, job strain, workplace social support, satisfaction with life, stress, resilience, aggression, mindfulness, and quality of life. Additionally, mindfulness training through the app has resulted in developing new, nonjudgmental attitudes toward experiences and

recognizing accessible choices. The app's availability, convenience, time commitment, affordability, and ease of use make it a promising tool for improving the mental well-being of first responders.

More recently, mobile apps have been successfully used to provide resources and mental health support to those in need. The availability, convenience, time commitment, affordability, and ease of use of digital tools for mindfulness training, such as smartphone apps with a mindfulness focus, can potentially improve public health (Economides et al., 2018; O'Daffer et al., 2022; Willis et al., 2020) and increase quality of life (van Emmerik et al., 2018). A randomized control trial [RCT] by Economides et al., (2018) suggested that brief mindfulness training via the smartphone app is an effective delivery medium for mindfulness training and has a beneficial impact on psychosocial well-being.

Implementing Headspace for first responders can help them build mindfulness skills that can be used to manage stress and improve their overall well-being. In 14 RCTs, Headspace use improved depression in 75% of the studies that evaluated it as an outcome (O'Daffer et al., 2022). Improvements in global well-being, anxiety, and depression, job strain, workplace social support, satisfaction with life, stress and resilience, aggression, mindfulness, and quality of life were seen in participants using the Headspace app (Bostock et al., 2019; Champion et al., 2018; DeSteno et al., 2018; Quinones & Griffiths., 2019; Rosen et al., 2018). Overall, implementing Headspace for first responders can help them build mindfulness skills that can be used to manage stress and improve their overall well-being. Ensuring first responders have the support and resources to effectively use the app and incorporate mindfulness into their daily routines is essential.

Methods

The purpose of this project was to assess perceived stress levels and mindful awareness in first responders by measuring a pre-PSS-10 and MAAS-15 survey, implementing the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app, and measuring a post-PSS-10 and MAAS-15 survey to evaluate the scale effectiveness of participants outcomes.

Design

A quality improvement pathway was used to meet the project's goals. The Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidenced Based Practice Model guided all aspects of this project.

Setting

This project was implemented at a local law enforcement agency in Los Angeles County, chartered in 1908. This agency is budgeted for 186 sworn personnel and 92 civilian support personnel. The Department has multiple resources, such as specially trained canine teams, directed enforcement units, scientific services investigators, bike teams, community affairs, fiscal services, and recruitment. (Inglewood Police Department, 2023)

Sample

The sample for this pilot project was thirteen sworn and civilian personnel who met the inclusion criteria and agreed to participate in the study. The inclusion criteria included all sworn personnel who are first responders and have been first responders during their employment with the agency, all civilian personnel who are first responders, and dispatchers who dispatch emergency calls to patrol officers. Inclusion criteria also included being 18 years or older, employed by the agency, and having a smartphone. The participants were informed of the risks and benefits of their involvement in the project.

Institutional Review Board Approval

The project lead sought IRB approval from California State University, Los Angeles, which was granted before the project's implementation (figure 4). A letter of support from the agency was also obtained, as shown in figure 5. Participation in this project was voluntary. Participants could drop out at any time. The project lead complied with all the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) requirements. All participants who participated in the project were provided with informed consent. All information will be kept confidential and, in a password, -protected laptop in a locked office.

Planning

In planning this pilot project, the project lead met with critical stakeholders of the project site (The agency's chief, the managers of the civilians, and the watch commanders). The project lead sent a mass email, shown in figure 6, to all sworn and civilian personnel who met the inclusion criteria. Participants who agreed to participate were provided consent by participating. Participants completed a pre-intervention questionnaire, the PSS-10, which asks about their feelings and perceived stress (Champion et al., 2018), and the MAAS-15 to assess their core characteristics of mindfulness (McDonald et al., 2021).

The project lead trained each participant on using the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app and required them to use it for 10 minutes daily for 21 days (about 3 weeks). This meditation instructed the participants to sit or lie quietly while listening to the calming short podcasts narrated by the Headspace app. After the 21-day meditation, participants completed an online post-intervention questionnaire, the PSS-10, and the MAAS-15. The project lead compared each participant's pre- and post-questionnaires.

Measures

The project lead used the PSS-10 and MAAS-15 and compared each participant's pre- and post-questionnaires. The PSS-10 gauges how likely a person will see certain circumstances in their life as stressful. The 10-item scale measures respondents' perceptions of their lives as unpredictable, unmanageable, and overloaded compared to the previous month. Respondents used a 5-point Likert scale to answer questions about their emotions and thoughts (0 = never to 4 = very often). Higher ratings indicated more stress. Ratings range from 0 to 40. The scale's validity with other measures ranges from .52 to .76 and has strong test-retest reliability =.85 (Champion et al., 2018). The 15-item MAAS is a reliable and valid measure of dispositional MA with good internal consistency $s = .82-.87$, convergent validity with other mindfulness measures $rs = .31-.33$, $ps .0001$, and convergent validity with measures of emotional well-being $rs = .16-.40$, $ps .01$ (Brown & Ryan, 2003).

Data Analysis

Through Qualtrics, the pre-and post-PSS-10 and the MAAS-15 survey link were emailed to participants. The participants received the pre-intervention survey one week before the first online education session began. After the online 21-day instruction session, the post-intervention questionnaire was distributed.

The means and standard deviations before and after the intervention were compared using a t-test. A paired t-test examined the differences in the pre- and post-PSS-10 and MAAS-15 scores. Statistical analysis is based on the alpha level of 0.05, and the findings are considered significant if the p-value is <0.05 . All data was analyzed using Intellectus Statistics for statistical analysis. It took 14 days (about 2 weeks) to compare the data.

Results

Thirteen out of 200 participants completed the intervention. Five (38%) were males, seven (54%) were females, and one (8%) preferred not to answer. One (8%) participant was between the ages of 18-29, six (46%) were between the ages of 30-39, four (31%) were between the ages of 40-49, and two (15%) were fifty or older. Two (15%) participants were Asian, six (46%) were African American/Black, three (23%) were Hispanic/Latino, one (8%) was Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander, and one (8%) White non-Hispanic. Five (38%) had one to five years in Public Service or Law Enforcement. Three (23%) had six-10 years, two (15%) had 11-15, and two (15%) had 16-20 years, and one (8%) had greater than 21 years in Public Service or Law Enforcement. Three (23%) participants have their High School Diploma. One (8%) participant has an associate degree. Four (31%) participants have a bachelor's degree. Five (38%) participants have a **master's** degree (Figure 6).

PSS-10 Results

The results were determined by comparing the cumulative pre- and post-PSS-10 scale scores. A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference between pre-PSS-10 and post-PSS-10 was significantly different from zero. The two-tailed paired samples *t*-test result was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(9) = 6.00$, $p < .001$, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected. This finding suggests that the difference in the mean of pre-PSS-10 and the mean of post-PSS-10 was significantly different from zero. The mean of pre-PSS-10 was significantly higher than the mean of post-PSS-10 (Figure 7).

MAAS-15 Results

A two-tailed paired sample *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference between pre-MAAS-15 and post-MAAS-15 was significantly different from zero. The results of

the Shapiro-Wilk test were significant based on an alpha value of .05, $W = 0.69$, $p < .001$. The two-tailed paired samples t-test result was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t_{14} = -6.50$, $p < .001$. This finding suggests that the difference in the mean of pre-MAAS -15 and the mean of post-MAAS-15 was significantly different from zero. The mean of pre-MAAS-15 was significantly lower than the mean of post-MAAS-15 (Figure 8).

Discussion

This quality improvement project aimed to investigate the effect of using the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app on stress reduction and mindfulness enhancement in first responders at a local law enforcement agency located in Los Angeles County, in southern California. The results revealed a significant decrease in mean scores between Pre-PSS-10 and post-PSS-10 assessments, indicating a reduction in perceived stress levels, alongside a significant decrease in mean scores between pre-MAAS-15 and post-MAAS-15 assessments, indicating an improvement in mindfulness levels following the intervention.

The significant decrease in mean scores on the -10 and MAAS-15 scales suggests positive outcomes associated with using the Headspace app. The reduction in perceived stress levels aligns with the goal of stress reduction interventions and may have important implications for individuals experiencing stress-related symptoms. Similarly, the improvement in mindfulness levels indicates that participants experienced an enhancement in present-moment awareness and non-judgmental acceptance of thoughts and emotions.

The findings from the quality improvement project are consistent with previous research demonstrating the effectiveness of mindfulness interventions in reducing perceived stress and enhancing mindfulness levels. Studies examining similar interventions, including other mindfulness apps and in-person mindfulness training programs, have reported comparable results. This consistency strengthens the evidence supporting the beneficial effects of mindfulness practices on psychological well-being.

Recommendations

Promoting Mindfulness Interventions at law enforcement agencies will encourage individuals experiencing stress or seeking to improve mindfulness to consider incorporating

mindfulness interventions, such as the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app, into their daily routines. The accessibility and user-friendly nature of mobile apps are convenient tools for practicing mindfulness exercises.

Integrate mobile mindfulness interventions like Headspace into stress management programs and on how to effectively use these apps to reduce perceived stress and enhance mindfulness levels among participants. Offer training and educational resources to individuals employed by agencies interested in implementing mindfulness interventions. Provide information on the benefits of mindfulness practices, evidence-based strategies for incorporating mindfulness into daily life, and guidance on selecting and using mindfulness apps effectively.

Ensure that mindfulness resources, including mobile apps like Headspace, are accessible and part of the agency's benefits package for employees. Advocate for policies and initiatives that support the integration of mindfulness into workplace settings. Raise awareness about the benefits of mindfulness for employees and advocate for funding and resources to support sustainable implementation.

Limitations

Despite the significant findings, this study had some limitations that should be considered. The sample size was small, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Moreover, the reliance on self-report measures, such as the PSS-10 and MAAS-15 scales, introduces the potential for response bias and social desirability effects. Additionally, to accommodate the time constraints of law enforcement personnel, email communication was utilized to send reminders for the successful completion of this project.

Implications for practice

This quality improvement project's findings have important implications for individuals and first responders interested in mindfulness interventions. For individuals seeking to reduce perceived stress and improve mindfulness levels, the Headspace app offers a convenient and accessible tool for practicing mindfulness exercises. First responders and organizations may also consider integrating mobile mindfulness interventions like Headspace into their wellness programs to promote psychological well-being among their employees. Future research should further explore the long-term effects of mobile mindfulness interventions and investigate their effectiveness in diverse populations and settings.

Conclusion

This quality improvement project provides evidence for the effectiveness of the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app in reducing perceived stress and enhancing mindfulness levels among first responders. The significant improvements observed on the PSS-10 and MAAS-15 scales underestimate the potential of mobile mindfulness interventions in promoting psychological well-being. By addressing the limitations and building on this project's findings, future research can continue to advance our understanding of the role of mobile technology in facilitating mindfulness practices and stress reduction strategies. The structured approach utilized in the DNP project, along with the comprehensive literature review and theoretical framework, reflects a holistic and evidence-based strategy to address the mental health needs of first responders.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence Based Practice Model

Figure 1

Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence Based Practice Model

Dang et al., 2022

Figure 1.2: Permission to use Johns Hopkins EBP (Evidence Based Practice) Model

Figure 1.2

Permission to use the Johns Hopkins EBP Model

JOHNS HOPKINS EBP MODEL AND TOOLS- PERMISSION

✓

Thank you for your submission.
We are happy to permit you to use the Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice model and tools to adhere to our legal terms noted below.
No further permission for use is necessary.

You may not modify the model or the tools without written approval from Johns Hopkins.
All references to source forms should include "© 2022 Johns Hopkins Health System/Johns Hopkins School of Nursing."
The tools may not be used for commercial purposes without special permission.
If interested in commercial use or discussing changes to the tool, please email jjhn@jhmi.edu.

Available Downloads:

- [📄 2022 JHEBP Tools \(printable\)](#)
- [📄 2022 JHEBP Tools \(fillable\)](#)
- [📄 2022 JHEBP Tools- Spanish](#)
- [📄 2022 JHEBP Tools- Chinese](#)
- [📄 2022 JHEBP Tools- Portuguese](#)

EBP Skill Build: This 3-day virtual workshop gives you a front-row seat to our EBP training and provides every participant with the guidance and support they need to get their EBP projects started.

Appendix B

Figure 2: Perceived Stress Scale

Figure 2

Perceived Stress Scale

Perceived Stress Scale - 10 items (PSS-10)[®]

INSTRUCTIONS:

The questions in this scale ask you about your feelings and thoughts during **THE LAST MONTH**. In each case, please indicate your response by placing an "X" over the circle representing **HOW OFTEN** you felt or thought a certain way.

3|

	Never 0	Almost Never 1	Sometimes 2	Fairly Often 3	Very Often 4
1. In the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	<input type="radio"/>				
2. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
3. In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and "stressed"?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?	<input type="radio"/>				
9. In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that were outside your control?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	<input type="radio"/>				

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PSS-10 – United States/English
PSS-10_AU2.0_eng-USori.doc

Figure 2.1 Permission to use Perceived Stress Scale

Figure 2.1

Permission to use Perceived Stress Scale

The **Perceived Stress Scale 10 Items (PSS10)** is Copyrighted.

Per the PSS Guidelines, "PSS can be used without permission and without fee for use for nonprofit educational or research purposes, including use in student projects. However, we do charge for use of the scale in mobile, website or other applications when application users are charged a fee."

Please email our team at HEAL_CDE@hsc.utah.edu to obtain access if this measure will be used within a nonprofit educational or research purposes.
English and Spanish CRFs are available.

However, if this measure is used within a for-profit organization or used within mobile, website or other applications when application users are charged a fee, please see below.

To access this measure, please contact Mapi Research Trust: <https://eprovide.mapi-trust.org/instruments/perceived-stress-scale-10-items>

Or

Register with American Sociological Association (ASA) (permissions@asanel.org) to obtain a license for this measure.

When applying for access on Mapi Research Trust, please indicate that you are conducting research as part of the NIH HEAL Initiative:

"Our study is a NIH funded study. We are part of the HEAL Initiative."

Once you have license permission, please share your email confirmation with HEAL_CDE@hsc.utah.edu for access to the NIH HEAL Initiative's CDE for this measure.

Appendix C

Figure 3: Mindful Attention Awareness Scale

Figure 3

Mindful Attention Awareness Scale

	1 Almost Always	2 Very Frequently	3 Somewhat Frequently	4 Somewhat Infrequently	5 Very Infrequently	6 Almost Never				
I could be experiencing some emotion and not be conscious of it until some time later.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I break or spill things because of carelessness, not paying attention, or thinking of something else.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I find it difficult to stay focused on what's happening in the present.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I tend to walk quickly to get where I'm going without paying attention to what I experience along the way.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I tend not to notice feelings of physical tension or discomfort until they really grab my attention.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I forget a person's name almost as soon as I've been told it for the first time.					1	2	3	4	5	6
It seems I am "running on automatic," without much awareness of what I'm doing.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I rush through activities without being really attentive to them.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I get so focused on the goal I want to achieve that I lose touch with what I'm doing right now to get there.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I do jobs or tasks automatically, without being aware of what I'm doing.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I find myself listening to someone with one ear, doing something else at the same time.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I drive places on 'automatic pilot' and then wonder why I went there.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I find myself preoccupied with the future or the past.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I find myself doing things without paying attention.					1	2	3	4	5	6
I snack without being aware that I'm eating.					1	2	3	4	5	6

Figure 3.1 Permission to use Mindful Attention Awareness Scale

Figure 3.1

Permission to use Mindful Attention Awareness Scale

Dear Colleague,

The trait Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) is in the public domain and special permission is not required to use it for research or clinical purposes. The trait MAAS has been validated for use with college student and community adults (Brown & Ryan, 2003), and for individuals with cancer (Carlson & Brown, 2005). A detailed description of the trait MAAS, along with normative score information, is found below, as is the scale and its scoring. A validated state version of the MAAS is also available in Brown and Ryan (2003) or upon request.

Feel free to e-mail me with any questions about the use or interpretation of the MAAS. I would appreciate hearing about any clinical or research results you obtain using the scale.

Yours,

Kirk Warren Brown, PhD
Department of Psychology
Virginia Commonwealth University
806 West Franklin St.
Richmond, VA 23284-2018
e-mail kwbrown@vcu.edu

Appendix D

IRB (Institutional Review Board) Approval

IRB Approval

Office Memorandum

DATE:	November 17, 2023
TO:	Raymund Gantioque
FROM:	Karina Martinez
PROJECT TITLE:	[2077160-1] Headspace: A Mindfulness Mobile App for Stress Reduction in First Responders
REFERENCE #:	23-15X
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS
DECISION DATE:	November 17, 2023
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Exemption category #2(i) and #2(ii)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Karina Martinez. **It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.**

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

Appendix E

Figure 4: Letter of Support

Figure 4

Letter of Support

Inglewood Police Department

CARDELL HURT
ACTING CHIEF OF POLICE

EDWARD M. RIDENS
DEPUTY CHIEF
MARIE DIBERNARDO
CAPTAIN
NEAL COCHRAN
ACTING CAPTAIN

May 12, 2023

This letter is to show that, I, Cardell Hurt, as the Acting Chief of Inglewood Police Department at 1 W. Manchester Blvd, Inglewood, California, 90302, give permission to Anika N. Simpson to conduct the project titled HEADSPACE: A Mindfulness Mobile App for Stress Reduction in First Responders on the following unit(s) Inglewood Police Department.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Acting Chief of Inglewood Police Department, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- (1) collect data (i.e. Demographics, pre-post surveys, Perceived Stress Scale, Mindful Attention Awareness Scale)
- (2) access necessary documents/data
- (3) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project (briefing's)
- (4) distribute pre-post surveys using the staff email

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are following the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at Inglewood Police Department and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

CARDELL HURT
Acting Chief of Police

Signature:
Name: Anika Simpson
Title: Doctor of Nursing Practice Student
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(323) 209-7312

Appendix F

Table 1: Participant Sociodemographic

Table 1

Participant Sociodemographic

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Male	5	38%
Female	7	54%
Prefer Not To Answer	1	8%
Age		
18-29	1	8%
30-39	6	46%
40-49	4	31%
50+	2	15%
Education		
High School Diploma	3	23%
Associate Degree	1	8%
Bachelor's Degree	4	31%
Master's Degree	5	38%
Ethnicity		
Asian	2	15%
AA/Black	6	46%
Hispanic/Latino	3	23%
Native Hawaiian/Pacific Island	1	8%
White/Non-Hispanic	1	8%
Years in Public Service		
1-5	5	38%
6-10	3	23%
11--15	2	15%
16-20	2	15%
20+	1	8%

Appendix G

Figure 6: Mean Pre and Post PSS-10 scores

Figure 6

The means of Pre- and Post-PSS-10 with 95.00% CI Error Bars

Appendix H

Table 2: T-test Pre and Post PSS-10 scores

Table 2

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre- and Post-PSS-10

Pre-PSS-10		Post-PSS-10		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
3.20	0.63	2.40	0.52	6.00	< .001	1.90

Note. N = 10. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 9. *D* represents Cohen's *d*.

Appendix I**Figure 7: Mean Pre and Post MAAS-15 scores****Figure 7**

The means of Pre- and Post-MAAS-15

Appendix J

Table 3: T-tests Pre and Post MAAS-15 scores

Table 3

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre and Post_MAAS-15

Pre_MAAS-15		Post_MAAS-15		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
3.87	0.52	4.73	0.70	-6.50	< .001	1.68
<i>Note.</i> N = 15. Degrees of Freedom for the <i>t</i> -statistic = 14. <i>d</i> represents Cohen's <i>d</i> .						

